

MESOPP

Potential update on the definition of taxonomic/functional/energetic group in MESOPP models in relation to new acoustic technology information

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Overview of MESOPP project

The underlying concept of MESOPP is the creation of a collaborative network and associated e-infrastructure (marine ecosystem information system) between European and Australian research teams/institutes sharing similar interests in: the Southern Ocean (SO) and Antarctica, its marine ecosystem functioning and the rapid changes occurring with the climate warming and the exploitation of marine resources.

In the past 30 years – facing global knowledge issues, lacking data and addressing huge modelling challenges – we observed the successful world organisation of meteorology. These past 15 years, Europe has kick started and achieved successful structuring of the operational oceanography fostered by the Copernicus initiative (<http://marine.copernicus.eu/>). Today, this structure is used and recognised worldwide and is integrated in GOOS (Global Ocean Observing System), IOOS (Integrated ocean observation system), SOOS (Southern Ocean Observing System), GODAE (the International Global Ocean Data Assimilation Experiment), and IMBER (Integrated Marine Biogeochemistry and Ecosystem Research).

The next major R&D strategic challenge is to connect the marine ecosystem community across the fields of meteorology, climate, oceanography and biology. This is a critical pre-requisite to overcoming (i) the domain's lack (or patchiness) of data, (ii) development of accurate high end to end models, (iii) global coverage and the need for exchange.

The objective of the MESOPP project is to meet this challenge and create links across the fields, pulling the marine ecosystem together. In particular, to:

1. Make an inventory of science challenges, stakes and existing policies and develop tools to federate and structure the community;
2. Start to organise the related marine ecosystem community between the EU and Australia through two implementation actions
3. Propose a R&D roadmap to support a large international cooperation on marine ecosystems based on an e-infrastructure, adding additional countries such as USA, New Zealand, Canada (in the Frame of the Galway statement), Brazil and all active countries already involved in large organisations such as IMBER, CCAMLR or IMOS.

MESOPP will focus on the enhancement of collaborations by eliminating various obstacles in establishing a common methodology and a connected network of databases of acoustic data for the estimation of micronekton biomass and validation of models. It will also contribute to a better predictive understanding of the SO based on furthering the knowledge base on key functional groups of micronekton and processes which determine ecosystem dynamics from physics to large oceanic predators.

This first project and associated implementation (science network and specification of an infrastructure) should constitute the nucleus of a larger international program of acoustic monitoring and micronekton modelling to be integrated in the general framework of ocean observation following a roadmap that will be prepared during the project.

1. Introduction

Ecosystem models typically output predictions of biomass and/or abundance split into taxonomical/functional/energetic groups (Constable et al. 2017). Assessment of predicted mid-trophic-level biomass could be carried out using active-acoustic observations, e.g. scientific echosounder observations, but this process requires that the predicted biomass of each model group is converted into echo intensity, summed over all of the groups, and then compared with spatially-averaged echosounder observations (Proud, Handegard, N. O. Pethybridge, et al. 2018). Presently, the conversion step generates large uncertainty because the model groups are comprised of a mixture of acoustic scattering groups (e.g. gas-bladdered, fluid-filled, tissue-based etc.) that can not be resolved independently.

To reduce this uncertainty, echosounder observations need to be split into groups that correspond to ecosystem model groups e.g. generic fish and zooplankton groups. To do this, more information is required relating to the length-frequency and presence/absence of species by depth and by functional group e.g. obtained using multi-frequency echosounder observations coupled with optics, environmental DNA (eDNA) and trawl data. However, each instrument and observation technique, including observations made using echosounders, is selective, and typically does not observe the full size range of different species equally and is therefore biased (Pakhomov & Yamamura 2010, Kaartvedt et al. 2012, Sutton et al. 2018).

1.1. Echosounder observations

Echosounder observations are typically made using hull-mounted instruments on research and fishing vessels (Simmonds & MacLennan 2005). The incident frequencies of vessel acoustics are usually between 18 and 200 kHz, giving an observation range of between c. 200 m (at 200 kHz) and > 5000 m (at 18 kHz). Mesopelagic research has typically been carried out by analysing 38 kHz data (c. 1000 m range), but some studies have incorporated lower frequencies (e.g. Godø et al. 2009). Although low frequencies are useful for the detection of larger organisms (> 4 cm), they do not detect or provide much information regarding smaller fluid-filled zooplankton. The use of both low and mid-frequency (> 38 kHz) echosounders could potentially provide enough information to distinguish between Rayleigh (small relative to wavelength), geometric (large relative to wavelength) and gas-bladdered organisms by analysis of their frequency response. Until recently, however, the majority of data has been collected from surface platforms, such as vessels, which are unable to collect good quality (high signal-to-noise ratio) high-frequency (>70 kHz) echosounder observations at depth due to sound attenuation in the water-column.

Recent technological advances have made it possible to operate echosounders semi-autonomously using deep-sea probes and underwater vehicles (e.g. Marouchos et al. 2016). Such devices, which are often coupled with other instruments (e.g. cameras), are able to make *in-situ* mid-to-high frequency echosounder observations of communities deep in the water-column; lower frequency echosounders are typically too large to attach to probes and underwater vehicles. Recent studies have shown good agreement between vessel and probe acoustics and have successfully partitioned echo intensity into gas-bladdered and non-gas-bladdered targets by using acoustic scattering models (Kloser et al. 2016). By combining both

vessel and probe acoustics, it is possible to distinguish between different scattering groups, in the same way that near-surface organisms, such as krill, are detected using multi-frequency vessel acoustics (Jarvis et al. 2010).

1.2. Trawl samples

Trawl samples are subject to sampling bias and selectivity. Typically, for mid-water trawls, two sources of bias are trawling speed and mesh size. Mesh size typically reduces between the mouth of the net and the cod-end. When sampling different size classes of organisms that are within the size range of the trawl net mesh size, the sampled volume, typically calculated using the mouth opening, is not the true sampled volume, since some of the organisms will escape by swimming through the mesh. In addition, larger organisms, capable of freely swimming, can avoid the net entirely (Kaartvedt et al. 2012). The extent of this bias is directly related to the gear type, trawl speed and size of organism. Therefore, sampling of micronekton (2 cm – 20 cm) using, for example, a Midwater Opening and Closing cod-end device (Sutton et al. 2018), where the mesh size varies between 10 and 20 cm (to capture the full range of micronekton organisms), is subject to species and size-specific bias and selectivity. Consequently, any biomass estimates calculated using trawl data should be used with caution, as the sampled biomass has high uncertainty and due to the above will almost certainly be an underestimate of the true value, for example, it has been estimated that for mesopelagic fish, trawl-derived biomass estimates may underestimate the true value by a factor of 7 or more (Koslow et al. 1997, Kloser et al. 2009, Yasuma & Yamamura 2010, Davison 2011, Kaartvedt et al. 2012). Furthermore, fragile, gelatinous organisms, will be fragmented by the trawl net (again a function of trawl speed, gear type and mesh size) and estimates of their biomass are very uncertain.

1.3. Optics and eDNA

Observations made using optics (e.g. stereo-photography and videography) and environment DNA analysis (screening *in-situ* water samples for residual DNA of sequenced organisms) can presently provide information on the presence/absence of species (Ryan et al. 2009, Rees et al. 2014, Barnes & Turner 2016, Marouchos et al. 2016, Goldberg et al. 2016); whilst both can also offer abundance, there is large uncertainty around such estimates. Both methods incur biases, but importantly, presence/absence information compliment acoustic observations and data obtained from trawl samples very well. Optics naturally require light, and light intensity and frequency, akin to the mesh size and speed of trawling, result in species and size-specific bias e.g. some fish, crustaceans and squid species may be attracted to the light, whilst other species may avoid or have no attraction. Critically though, optics provides a means to observe and size gelatinous organisms, which are heavily under-sampled by nets and, that may also cause a significant proportion of the received echo intensity (e.g. gas-bearing siphonophores at low frequencies). Similarly, eDNA can also provide presence/absence data but is not limited by size range or field of view but does require that the DNA of the organism is known.

1.4. Links to ecosystem models

Ecosystem models are built on current knowledge (e.g. energy transfer and growth) that may be significantly constrained by observations. Observations that drive ecosystem models are typically at low or high trophic-levels. This is because the bias and variance of satellite-inferred net primary production or top predator abundance/biomass is thought to be relatively well-understood and can be quantified. Consequently, the dynamics of mid-trophic-level organisms are not constrained or assessed, which impacts model-predicted predator-prey interactions and carbon flux in the water-column (both actively through vertical migration and passively via sinking matter). Recently, there has been increased interest in estimates of micronekton (2 cm to 20 cm) biomass, particularly of fish (Irigoien et al. 2014, Proud, Handegard, Kloser, et al. 2018), as a potential protein resource for human consumption and/or feed for aquaculture and agriculture (St. John et al. 2016). Hence, ecosystem model predictions that do not provide associated uncertainty have come under scrutiny. We propose to address this by combining observations from a multitude of instruments of mid-trophic-level organisms, to reduce the overall bias and quantify uncertainty, which could be used to assess or constrain ecosystem models. The difficulty in this task is that ecosystem models typically produce biological metrics, e.g. energy, biomass, abundance, whilst observations come in a variety of indirect metrics e.g. echo intensity, imagery, biological samples, species presence/absence data etc. The challenge, therefore, is to build an objective observation model that incorporates observations from many instruments, to reduce bias in estimates of micronekton biomass and population dynamics (e.g. length-frequency distributions).

1.5. This report

We propose that observations made from vessel acoustics, self-contained/remotely operated probes and underwater vehicles, coupled with trawl and net data, could provide enough information to provide an unbiased (relatively) estimate of biomass, corresponding taxonomically/functionally to groups output by ecosystem models. In this report, we describe the Profiling Lagrangian Acoustic Optical System (PLAOS) and discuss how measurements of echo energy at multiple frequencies, coupled with optics and trawl samples, could be used to estimate the biomass and length-frequency distribution of mesopelagic fish. We then update the ecosystem model assessment framework described in a previous MESOPP report (Proud, Handegard, N. O. Pethybridge, et al. 2018) and discuss future work.

2. An acoustic-based coupled open-ocean observing system

Satellites can provide measurements of ocean colour and sea-surface temperature and using models (supported with process studies) the biomass of low-trophic-level organisms such as phytoplankton can be predicted (e.g. Behrenfeld & Falkowski 1997). Large oceanic predators are tagged and monitored for population biomass estimates (e.g. Bestley et al. 2008). These two start and end components of oceanic food-webs provide the foundation of much of our ecosystem modelling through bottom-up and top-down control with inherent bias and uncertainty (Fulton et al. 2011). What is now required, are observations of the mid-trophic-level organisms to both constrain and assess ecosystem models. Acoustics, optics and trawl

samples can all provide information relating to mid-trophic-level organisms but are often used separately and therefore are associated with large uncertainty and bias due to instrument-specific selectivity. Coupling these observations reduces that bias, which has led to the call for an acoustic-based coupled observation and modelling system for monitoring and predicting ecosystem dynamics of the open ocean (Handegard et al. 2013). Due to recent advancements in coupled acoustic-optical systems (e.g. PLAOS) that can gather *in-situ* observations of the mesopelagic community, we can now start to better understand and compensate for the selectivity and bias in micronekton observations.

2.1. Midwater trawls

Midwater trawls provide important samples of mesopelagic micronekton (2 cm – 20 cm). Due to escapement and avoidance and the destruction of fragile gelatinous organisms, trawl samples provide a biased (e.g. underestimate) estimate of the true micronekton biomass and disproportionate length-frequency distributions. However, the important information that can be ascertained from trawl samples, includes 1.) specific components of species length-frequency distributions, where the bias is known or estimated for a given size range; 2.) length-weight relationships, often less biased than length-frequency and are critical for biomass estimation, and 3.) proportion of gas-bladdered fish to non-gas bladdered fish by length class. This final piece of information is required when estimating fish biomass using acoustics (Figure 1), but critically, this assumes that there are no other gas-bladdered organisms present or that the number of other gas-bladdered organisms is known. Since we know that gas-bladdered siphonophores are observed almost ubiquitously in the open-ocean from observations made using both nets and optics (Barham 1963, Musayeva 1976, Mackie et al. 1988, Robison et al. 1998, Lavery et al. 2007), but cannot quantify them due to heavy sampling biases, a means to estimate their abundance is urgently required (Proud, Handegard, Kloser, et al. 2018).

Figure 1: Composite biological and acoustic data plot of mid-water trawl results. Taken from Sutton et al. (2018) Figure 3-26. Fish biomass estimates are typically made by using a combination of both techniques.

2.2. PLAOS

The Profiling Lagrangian Acoustic Optical System (PLAOS, Figure 2) was borne out of existing CSIRO technology (Ryan et al. 2009, Kloser et al. 2009, Sherlock et al. 2010, Marouchos et al. 2016). It is a free-floating system that moves with the current capable of performing vertical profiles at speeds of between c. 0.1 and 0.4 ms⁻¹, collecting acoustic observations (38, 120 and 333 kHz) and imagery (both stills and video). PLAOS is also fitted with a SBE37/DO CTD, which makes measurements of salinity and temperature used for both physical oceanography and to calculate sound speed/absorption to calibrate the echosounders.

Figure 2: Image and schematic of Profiling Lagrangian Acoustic Optical System (PLAOS) adapted from Marouchos et al. (2016). The system weighs c. 700 kg (in air) is 3.2 m tall and 1.4 m in diameter.

2.2.1. PLAOS acoustics

PLAOS has split-beam 38, 120 and 333 kHz transducers, each linked to their own separate transceiver operating in both narrow and broadband frequency modes (see Figure 2). The system also contains a broad-spectrum hydrophone that passively collects surrounding noise data. Before PLAOS is deployed, the echosounders are switched on and ping continuously throughout the mission.

Vessel acoustic observations of the mesopelagic community are restricted to lower frequencies (e.g. ≤ 70 kHz) due to water-column absorption. At these frequencies and depth ranges, small gas-bladdered organisms are likely to produce resonant scattering, which dominates the acoustic scattering and masks non-gas-bladdered organisms. Vessel acoustics can use multiple frequencies (e.g. 18, 38 and 70 kHz) to detect resonance volume scattering but higher frequencies and single target resolution is not possible. Using PLAOS, we are able to collect high-frequency (e.g. 120 and 333 kHz) echosounder observations of the mesopelagic community at depth on individual targets, which are not strongly affected by resonance

scattering and can be used in conjunction with other frequencies to determine scattering groups (e.g. differentiating between resonant, Rayleigh and geometric scatterers, see Proud, Handegard, Lehodey, et al., 2018).

Using PLAOS data collected on a survey in the Tasman Sea in 2008, Kloser et al. (2016) were able to identify gas-bladdered targets at close range (5-15 m) and estimate their density (see Figure 3). They estimated that these targets were responsible for at least 80-90% of the total water-column backscattering intensity at 38 kHz. Although the probe is capable of separating out acoustic signal into acoustic scattering groups, it cannot presently separate gas-bladdered targets into, for example, fish and siphonophores, to do this, more information is required.

Figure 3: Density of gas-bladdered targets by depth and equivalent spherical radius (ESR), based on data collected by PLAOS in the Tasman Sea (2008) and acoustic scattering models. Dashed line is minimum ESR detection capability. Taken from (Kloser et al. 2016).

2.2.2. PLAOS optics

The PLAOS optical system, which is depth rated to 1500 m, is comprised of a single video stream HD GBO technology S1080 camera and two independent 18 MP Canon 1DX DSLR digital stills cameras (Marouchos et al. 2016). The video camera is illuminated by a pair of

Deep-Sea Power and Light SeaLite sphere units and the stills cameras by a pair of quantum strobes. The stills cameras operate at a frequency of 1 Hz, one is positioned at the bottom of the frame facing downwards and has a wide-angled lens (18 mm) to gather a broad view of targets (left image in Figure 4), and the other is positioned higher up on the frame, also facing downwards but at an oblique angle, focused at a distance of 2 m to take close up images of backlit targets (right image of Figure 4).

The images collected during vertical profiles provide information on the presence/absence of species. However, this assumes that a species for a given size range does not avoid PLAOS.

Figure 4: Example imagery captured by PLAOS during a vertical water-column profile in the Tasman Sea (2008). Downward facing (left) and oblique (right) camera.

2.3. Conclusions

To estimate length-frequency distributions and biomass of mesopelagic fish, a number of concurrent and collocated observations and samples are required (see Table 1). Trawling provides partial length-frequency data along with length-weight and proportion of gas-bladdered to non-gas-bladdered fish, but no information on siphonophores. Vessel acoustics provides total water-column backscattering intensity, which can be attributed to gas-bladdered fish and siphonophores, whereas acoustic observations made using probes (e.g. PLAOS) can resolve the densities of gas-bladdered targets, but again, cannot split these targets into siphonophores and fish. Optics provides a means to obtain presence/absence data for siphonophores. Using this information, we can identify depth ranges where fish are numerically dominant and use the trawl and acoustic data to determine fish mean Target Strength (average amount of echo energy produced by an individual target) and use fish density to scale fish length-frequency distributions. This method assumes that the shape of the length-frequency distribution is known and that there are certain depth ranges where siphonophores are not present. However, given a high enough sampling effort both assumptions could be satisfied. If we can estimate the density and length-frequency distributions of mesopelagic fish, we should be able to use these estimates to assess predictions made by ecosystem models, which typically output size distributions and abundance/biomass values. The strength of this method is that it accommodates the inclusion

of new improved methods, e.g. broadband acoustics and stereo-photography for length measurements, to estimate species length frequencies.

Table 1. Information required to estimate mesopelagic fish biomass from vessel acoustic observations. Shading indicates that the sampling technique can presently (green) or in the future (orange) provide biometric information that is both selective and biased.

Sampling technique	Length distribution	Length-weight relationship	density	Proportion of gas-bladdered to non-gas-bladdered	Density of gas bladdered targets	Siphonophore presence
Probe acoustics						
Net/trawls						
optics						
Optics (stereo)						
eDNA						

3. Assessment of ecological models

Observations of low (e.g. phytoplankton) and/or high (e.g. top predators) trophic-level species are often used to assess, constrain and/or tune ecosystem models (e.g. Atlantis). Consequently, the mid-trophic-level components, their dynamics and biomass, are not likely to represent the actual communities that they portray, rather, they are forced to fit the design of the model. Since model predictions of mid-trophic-level biomass are required to feed into earth-system and climate models (to represent the biological carbon pump), these components need to be assessed, constrained and tuned by observations. We can combine biased and selective observations of the mesopelagic community (e.g. net/rawl data, acoustics, optics, eDNA etc.) to estimate length-frequency distributions and biomass of different groups of organisms. This observation-based length-frequency model is an improvement on the acoustic observation model described in previous MESOPP reports (Proud, Handegard, N. O. Pethybridge, et al. 2018). In the remainder of this chapter, the advantages of this model are discussed, and a new ecosystem model assessment framework is proposed.

3.1. The observation-based length-frequency model

The observation-based length-frequency model (OBLFM) incorporates all available observations (e.g. acoustic, optics and net data) and outputs length-frequency distributions of target groups (e.g. mesopelagic fish), which are directly comparable to outputs produced

by ecosystem models (Figure 5). Length-weight relationships (e.g. from trawl data) can then be used to estimate biomass. Critically, ecosystem models do not need to be modified to be compared to the OBLFM, nor do they need to provide any additional information e.g. proportion of gas-bladdered fish.

The OBLFM, conceptionally shown in Figure 5 for a given target group (e.g. mesopelagic fish) and depth layer (e.g. mesopelagic zone), is a data-hungry model that reduces bias as more observations are added. To quantify variance, repeat observations are required, and through increasing sampling effort, this variance may be reduced. The model performs optimally when the target group can be separated using multi-frequency acoustics and/or presence/absence information from optics and eDNA data. For example, if for a given depth layer there was a recorded absence of siphonophores then all of the gas-bladdered targets identified by the probe could be assigned to gas-bladdered fish. Since the proportion of gas-bladdered fish to non-gas-bladdered fish can be estimated from the trawl data, mean target strength of fish by length class can be calculated. If we assume the gas-bladdered organisms are responsible for the majority of echo intensity, then the length-frequency distribution can be estimated, and from that, biomass of fish using the weight-length relationship obtained from the trawl data. Importantly, the multi-frequency/broadband vessel and probe volume echo energy is used to constrain the biomass of the various taxa so that the total biomass of all groups is explained for all frequencies based on their frequency dependent echo energy.

Figure 5: The observation-based length-frequency model (OBLFM) for a given target group (e.g. mesopelagic fish) and depth layer. Biased observations are collated from a range of observations (e.g. trawls, acoustics, optics, eDNA) and combined to produce the most plausible length-frequency distribution.

3.2. Ecosystem model assessment framework

An ecosystem model assessment framework was described in a previous MESOPP report (Proud, Handegard, N. O. Pethybridge, et al. 2018), in which ecosystem model output was converted into echo energy before being compared to acoustic observations. The conversion of echo energy to abundance in this new approach, is now carried out within the OBLFM (Figure 5). The estimation of the target groups length-frequency distribution is compared with the ecosystem model predicted length-frequency distribution by, for example, using a two-sample Kolmogorov-Smirnov test (Figure 6). Results of the comparison can then be used to modify parameters that relate to the particular model group or used to tune initial conditions.

Figure 6: Ecosystem model assessment framework. Biased observations from multiple sources are assimilated in the observation-based length-frequency model and an estimate of target group length-frequency distribution is made. This is then compared to output predicted by an ecosystem model and the residual feeds back to optimize parameters/initial conditions. Biomass can also be compared by using a length-weight relationship obtained from, for example, trawl samples.

3.3. Conclusions

In this section, we have described a model that can assimilate all available observations to provide the best estimate of the length-frequency distribution of a given target group. This may be useful when estimating abundance of mesopelagic fish because presence/absence observations can potentially identify depth layers that have low siphonophore abundance. These depth layers could then be used to scale estimates of abundance (and biomass) of other depth layers. We replaced the acoustic observation model, described in a previous MESOPP report (Proud, Handegard, N. O. Pethybridge, et al. 2018), in our ecosystem model assessment framework with the OBLFM because it has several advantages over its predecessor: 1.) the OBLFM estimates biological metrics rather than producing echo energy values; 2.) the design and output of ecosystem models does not need to be modified – meaning that this assessment framework could theoretically be applied to any ecosystem model that produces abundance/biomass predictions, and 3.) any relevant observations can be incorporated into the OBLFM. The assessment of mid-trophic-level components of ecosystem models will provide fisheries and conservation management with confidence to enact policy, and critically, will quantify uncertainty in biomass predictions that feed into climate models to represent the biological carbon pump, an important component of the carbon cycle.

4. Discussion and Summary

Technological advances and the down-sizing of ocean instrumentation is paving the way for increased mid-water and deep *in-situ* observations of micronekton. Coupled acoustics, optics, eDNA data collected by vertically profiling ocean probes such as PLAOS, can provide a multitude of observations that have known selectivity and biases. Coupling these data with biological samples and other observational data, we can reduce overall bias in estimates of micronekton biomass and use those estimates to assess, initiate and assimilate into ecosystem models.

In this report, we have only proposed concepts and frameworks, what is needed now is the development of robust and rigorously tested methods that optimise the observation-based length-frequency model (OBLFM) described here. We have focused on mesopelagic fish groups, but the OBLFM will also provide estimates for crustaceans, squids and gelatinous organisms. These length-frequency estimates, once assimilated, could be used to assess other components of ecosystem models to test sensitivity of assumptions and implications for other prey groups, their biomass and trophic efficiency.

4.1. Implications

Improving the representation of the mesopelagic community in ecosystem models will improve our understanding of open-ocean ecosystem function and dynamics in a number of ways. We will gain better insight into modelled predator-prey interactions (e.g. included in the Atlantis modelling framework), particularly of deep-diving predators such as king penguins and elephant seals that forage on mesopelagic scattering layers (Proud & Brierley 2018). Tuned biomass of vertically migrating mesopelagic organisms will reduce uncertainty in estimates of actively-transported carbon in the water-column, i.e. the biological carbon

pump, which will directly impact our understanding of the global carbon budget. Improved biomass estimates of mesopelagic fish will aid future mesopelagic fisheries (and conservation) management, which is particularly important given recent increased commercial interest in the stock (St. John et al. 2016).

The implementation of the OBLFM, once tested, should provide a pathway to design a coupled observation and modelling system for open-ocean ecosystems (Handegard et al. 2010, 2013). The method is not reliant on a single observation method or technology but provides a framework of integrating all available information to derive the most plausible estimate of observed species length-frequency distributions and biomass. This will be an important component of any future monitoring road map for mesopelagic organisms.

4.2. Future work

In this report, we have proposed a new coupled observation and modelling system framework (Figures 5 and 6), built on the work published in previous MESOPP reports (e.g. Constable et al. 2017, Proud, Handegard, et al. 2018, Proud, Handegard, N. O. Pethybridge, et al. 2018). To move forward, a generic observation-based length-frequency model should be designed and published that is applicable to any observational data that incurs bias, and then the model should be tested for the specific case of mesopelagic organisms (driven by acoustics), for a number of species groups using a range of ecosystem models (e.g. Atlantis, SEAPODYM, MISER etc.). This could be carried out presently in the Tasman Sea, in the Great Australian Bight and in the Southern Ocean, where PLAOS, trawl samples and vessel acoustics have already been collected (see Kloser et al. 2016 and www.imos.org.au). Testing should include the use of different combinations of observations (including different acoustic frequencies) and biological samples to ascertain the sensitivity of the model under different data-driven scenarios. Using the results of this analysis, a coupled observation and modelling framework (or roadmap) could be constructed and implemented to guide and inform management and research scientists. Additionally, the method will need to be trialled in at a number of different regions and seasons. This will require the collection of more *in-situ* observations of mesopelagic organisms, including if possible, multi-frequency and broadband acoustic data coupled with stereo-optics (capable of length estimation) and video plankton recorder imagery (to capture smaller size groups).

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